

Randomized Genetically Modified Monoculture Degradation by *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium chrysogenum* on Varying Concentration of Spent Engine Oil

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ABSTRACT

The deleterious impact of spent engine oil on the environment has long been a cause for concern, given its persistent presence and harmful effects on ecosystems. In this study, we assessed the potential of genetically modified or engineered fungi (GMF) in the biodegradation of spent oil contaminated soil. Inoculation of *Aspergillus niger* (F1) and *Penicillium chrysogenum* (F2) on spent oil-contaminated soil samples at various concentrations (1%, and 5%) over a 28-day period was conducted. The optical density (OD) values of the various samples were analyzed over the observation period. Both F1 and F2 at 1% and 5% concentrations exhibited a significant decrease in OD values, indicating effective degradation of the spent oil. However, F1 showed a slower and more pronounced OD reduction compared to F2. Interestingly, F2 demonstrated a faster and more prominent reduction in optical density values, particularly during the later stages of the experiment, highlighting potentially superior efficacy compared with F1. These findings highlight the promise of these fungal isolates as viable candidates for bioremediation agents, showcasing their ability to contribute to environmentally friendly and sustainable solutions for hydrocarbon-rich pollutant cleanup.

Keyword: *Spent Engine Oil, Bioremediation, Hydrocarbon and Mutation*

INTRODUCTION

Engine oil could simply be defined as a thick mineral liquid applied to a machine or engine so as to reduce friction between the moving parts of a machine (Shahida *et al.*, 2015). Engine oil that principally functions as cleaning the motor engines, lubricating the moving parts of motor engines, inhibiting corrosion of motor engines, improving sealing and cooling the engine by transporting heat away from the moving parts (Tudararao-Aherobo and Mesogboriwon, 2020). The present-day engine oils are derivative of petroleum-based hydrocarbons and non-petroleum produced organic compounds, including some organometallic constituents that is used to lubricate parts of an automobile engine, in order to smoothened engine operation.

Spent engine oil is defined as used lubricating oils obtained after servicing and subsequently drained from automobile and generator engines. Spent engine oil is similar to unused oil, except that it contains additional chemicals that are produced or build up in the oil, when it is used as an engine lubricant at high temperatures and pressures, inside an engine as it runs (Eniola *et al.*, 2014), in fact engine oil is chemically transformed by oxidation, nitration, cracking of polymers and decomposition of metallic compounds. In addition spent engine oil contains different contaminants such as organo-metallic compounds whose synthesis is made possible via atmospheric dust, metals, metal oxides and combustion products (Ghribi *et al.*, 2018). Spent engine oil also contains other contaminants such as alkyl benzenes, naphthalene, methylnaphthalenes and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). The presence of these compounds makes UEO one of the most polluting, toxic, and dangerous waste products existing on Earth (Ghribi *et al.*, 2018).

Spent engine oil has been recognized as one of the most hazardous wastes that are discharged into the environment without being treated to remove its toxicity especially in developing countries such as Nigeria (Obi *et al.*, 2022). In Nigeria, it is common among motor mechanics to dispose of spent engine oil into gutters, water drains and soil, the indiscriminate dumping of spent engine oil will leads to dangerous environmental pollution and become potential threat to human, animals, soil and other vegetation (Dhanya, 2020).

In contemporary times, a variety of mechanical approaches are employed to address the remediation of dumped spent engine oil. Traditional methods encompass physical, chemical, and mechanical processes to restore contaminated areas. Among these, physical remediation techniques such as incineration, brick making, and the use of skimmers have been applied.

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However, these physical methods typically yield limited biodegradation results, typically achieving no more than 10-15% of oil spill remediation (Tudararao-Aherobo and Mesogboriwon, 2020). Conversely, the utilization of chemical surfactants as a remediation agent is less favored due to their adverse impact on the surrounding flora and fauna, rendering them ecologically undesirable (Tudararao-Aherobo and Mesogboriwon, 2020).

Crude oil is currently Nigeria's and of course, the world's main energy source (Agu *et al.*, 2015). Petroleum is simply a mixture of crude oil, condensate and natural gas. Crude oil is a complex mix of different molecular weight hydrocarbons made up of hydrogen and carbon in the ratio of 2:1. It is also composed of approximately 3% (v/v) nitrogen, oxygen and sulphur; trace amounts of phosphorus and heavy metals viz vanadium and nickel (Okafor *et al.*, 2016; Anaukwu *et al.*, 2016). Biodegradation stands out as an optimal choice for addressing environmental contamination, primarily due to its cost-effectiveness and widespread acceptance. This process harnesses the potential of microorganisms and their enzymes to thoroughly eliminate pollutants. The Niger Delta is among the top 10 most important wetlands and marine ecosystems on earth, whose ecosystem has been brutally devastated by petroleum contamination due largely to poor petroleum exploration (Mbachu *et al.*, 2014; Agu and Odibo, 2021). Biodegradation leverages the innate capabilities of microorganisms to convert toxic contaminants into less harmful components. The effectiveness of such endeavors relies on the presence of petrophilic microorganisms with the ability to break down a diverse range of compounds within the contaminant (Dhanya, 2020). A wide variety of microorganisms including algae, bacteria, fungi and yeasts have the ability to degrade hydrocarbons. However, bacterial community plays a pivotal role in bioremediation of hydrocarbon contamination. (Kumar *et al.*, 2014). They secrete different extracellular enzymes into their peripheral environment and degrade various substrates to small molecules that can be absorbed by and metabolized in their cells, the mycelial structure of these microorganisms is another advantage for bioremediation with its invasive nature which allows the investigation of a large volume of contaminated sites with a very large exchange surface (Benguenab, and Chibani, 2022)

The aim of the research is to assess the potential of genetically modified or engineered fungi in the biodegradation of spent engine oil

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preliminary Screening of Spent Engine Oil Degraders:

One gram (1g) of the soil samples was weighed out aseptically and introduced into 100ml of sterile Bushnell Haas Broth medium containing 2ml/L of spent engine oil for the screening of spent engine oil-degrading fungi. It was placed on a rotary shaker at a revolution speed of 90rpm for 7 days. Ten (10)-fold serial dilution was aseptically carried out on the samples on SDA and BHA. The culture plates were incubated at 25°C aerobically for 48-72 hours for the fungi. Developing colonies on SDA was counted to obtain total viable. Discrete colonies for the fungi were obtained by sub culturing into SDA plates and were subsequently identified using standard methods.

Fungal Identification

This was done based on the description of the gross morphological appearance of fungal colonies on the SDA culture medium and the modified slide culture technique using lactophenol cotton blue stain for the microscopic evaluation under X10 and X40 magnification of the microscope (Agu and Chidozie, 2021); with reference to the Manual of Fungal Atlases (Barnett and Hunter, 2000; Watanabe, 2002; Ellis *et al.*, 2007).

Genetic Modification

A 24h of the fungi subculture is exposed to 2h of UV light in an enclosed chamber on a daily basis for 7 days for a tentative random mutation.

Bushnell Haas Medium Broth composition (gL⁻¹)

Magnesium sulphate 0.200g, Calcium chloride anhydrous 0.020g, Potassium dihydrogen phosphate 1.000g, Dipotassium hydrogen phosphate 1.000g, Ammonium nitrate 1.000g, Ferric chloride 0.050g, Final pH (at 25°C) 7.0±0.2.

Bushnell Haas Medium Agar composition (gL⁻¹)

Magnesium sulphate 0.200g, Calcium chloride anhydrous 0.020g, Potassium dihydrogen phosphate 1.000g, Dipotassium hydrogen phosphate 1.000g, Ammonium nitrate 1.000g, Ferric chloride 0.050g, Agar 20.000g Final pH (at 25°C) 7.0±0.2.

Degradation by Monocultures

2 fungal plugs of the isolates were inoculated into separate 50ml of BHA broth containing varying concentrations (1% and 5%) of spent engine oil in 100ml flasks. They were then incubated at

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150rpm in a rotary shaker for 35 days at 30°C. The level of degradation was assessed through spectrophotometric analysis at 680nm, and pH measurements all of which were considered at 7-day intervals. Degradation was carried out at room temperature.

RESULTS

Table 4.1: Colonial Morphology and Microscopy of Fungi Isolates

Isolates	Colony morphology	Microscopy	Identity
F1	Colonies appear on SDA a powdery mass of black spores on the surface and light yellow in the reverse side. Incubated 30°C for 5 days	Conidial heads are large (up to 3 mm by 15 to 20 µm in diameter), globose, dark brown, becoming radiate and tending to split into several loose columns with age. Hyphal growth are thread-like Branching and producing Mycelium (3-6 µm in diameter) Conidiophore stipes are smooth-walled, hyaline or turning dark towards the vesicle. Conidial heads are biseriate with the phialides borne on brown, often septate metulae.	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
F2	Cultures on SDA are fluffy, bright yellowish green with bluish green tint, funiculose with bundles of hyphae, reverse yellowish pink with reddish purple tint. Rather good in growth	Conidiophore's hyaline, erect, developed from aerial hyphae, branched penicillately at the apexes with primary and secondary metulae, verticillate phialides and catenulate conidia in each phialide, forming rather open-spaced yellowish green conidial heads: phialides lanceolate or abruptly sharpened.	<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>

Table 4.2: pH values at Degradation Concentration 1% of Spent Engine Oil

	Day 0	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21	Day 28
F1	7.0 ± 0.015	6.71±0.006	6.32±0.015	5.67±0.015	CS
F2	7.0 ± 0.012	6.12±0.015	5.98±0.015	5.49±0.010	CS
Control	7.0 ± 0.010	7.0 ±0.010	7.0 ± 0.015	7.0± 0.060	7.0 ± 0.015

CS: clear solution (indicative of absolute degradation)

Table 4.3: pH values at Degradation Concentration 5% of Spent Engine Oil

	Day 0	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21	Day 28
F1	7.0 ±0.010	7.13 ±0.015	7.15±0.012	7.20 ±0.010	CS
F2	7.0 ±0.015	7.44 ±0.000	7.31±0.010	7.26 ± 0.012	CS
Control	7.0 ±0.000	7.0 ±0.010	7.0 ±0.000	7.0 ±0.010	7.0 ±0.010

CS: clear solution (indicative of absolute degradation)

Table 4.4: Optical density (680nm) values at Degradation Concentration 1% of Spent Engine Oil

	Day 0	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21	Day 28
F1	1.135 ±0.000	1.115 ±0.010	1.007 ±0.010	0.931±0.010	CS
F2	1.135 ±0.015	0.988 ±0.010	0.734 ±0.010	0.457±0.010	CS
Control	1.135 ±0.010	1.132 ±0.010	1.131± 0.010	1.125±0.015	1.120 ± 0.015

CS: clear solution (indicative of absolute degradation)

Table 4.5: Optical density (680nm) values at Degradation Concentration 5% of Spent Engine Oil

	Day 0	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21	Day 28
F1	1.441± 0.015	1.385 ± 0.012	1.364 ±0.010	1.287 ±0.010	
F2	1.441 ±0.010	1.401 ±0.010	1.140± 0.000	0.821 ± 0.015	
Control	1.441± 0.015	1.437 ±0.000	1.418± 0.010	1.405 ± 0.012	1.381 ±0.010

DISCUSSION

The deleterious impact of spent engine oil on the environment has long been a cause for concern, given its persistent presence and harmful effects on ecosystems. As a response to this environmental challenge, our study scrutinizes the potential of genetically engineered fungi (GMF) to mitigate the environmental impact of spent engine oil.

In this study, we investigated the microbiological aspects of spent engine oil degradation using genetically modified fungi across different concentrations (1%, and 5%). Degradation was measured by analyzing optical density (OD) values of the various samples over a 28-day period of inoculation, we uncover clear degradation patterns and the efficiency of microbial organisms involved in breaking down spent engine oil.

Table 1 presents the results of fungal isolates obtained through the culturing of contaminated soil samples. Two (2) fungi were identified they are: *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*. The results are in accordance with Adeleye (2018) which reported the presence of *Penicillium spp* from the consortia of isolate gotten from spent engine oil contaminated soil. Umana *et al* (2016) also reported the isolation *Penicillium chrysogenum* fungi in their work of bioremediation of spent engine oil by *Penicillium sp*. The fungi were isolated from spent engine oil contaminated soil obtained at the Uyo Mechanic village in Afa Ofot in Uyo Metropolis of Akwa Ibom State. Similarly, Adeogun and Adekunle (2015). Ameen *et al* (2015) in their study isolated *Aspergillus niger* from various hydrocarbon contaminated sites. The fungi isolated from this study have been reported as hydrocarbons utilizers (Obire *et al.* (2008); George-Okafor *et al.* (2009), Juhasz, A. L., and Naidu, R. (2000) and Omotayo *et al.* (2012) in their study also mentioned some soil borne

fungi such as *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* which were found to be potential degraders of crude oil hydrocarbons which is in conformity with this study.

In this study, biodegradation assays were conducted by inoculating fungi isolate *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium chrysogenum* on the contaminated soil samples at various concentrations, including 5% and 1%. This systematic approach allowed for a comprehensive assessment of the organisms' efficacy in degrading spent engine oil across different levels of soil contamination

Both F1 and F2 at various sample concentration (1% and 5%) exhibited a notable decrease in optical density over the observation period, indicating effective degradation of the spent engine oil. The consistent reduction in OD values also indicated that the degradation was primarily driven by the metabolic activities of *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*.

Penicillium chrysogenum (F2) appears to be the more efficient organism in the degradation of spent engine oil at both 1% and 5% concentration as it demonstrated a faster and more pronounced reduction in OD values, particularly during the later stages of the observation period, indicating potentially superior efficacy compared to *Aspergillus niger* (F1)

The findings in this study are in accordance with the study of Umana *et al.* (2016) where in vivo bioremediation assay using *Penicillium sp* and *T. occidentalis*. in biodegradation of spent engine oil contaminated soil was done at different concentrations of 20/180, 40/360, 60/540, 80/720 and 100ml/900mm. *Penicillium sp* was observed to more effective in the degradation of the spent engine oil. And agrees with the findings of Adekunle *et al.* (2004) that strains of the genus *Penicillium* are good hydrocarbon assimilators and that there has the ability to transform xenobiotics into less mutagenic products. Similarly, Abdusalam *et al.* (2013) also reported that *Penicillium sp* has the ability to degrade monocyclic aromatic hydro carbons such as benzene, toluene, ethyl benzene and xylene; BTEX), phenol compounds and heavy metals like lead, nickel and iron using mono-oxygenases, forming a trans-diol.

The effects of pH change for bioremediation using *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*. over the degradation period of 28 days are represented in Table 4.2. and 4.3. respectively. *Aspergillus niger* utilised the spent engine oil best at 1% concentration on the 14th day at 6.32 pH value and *Penicillium chrysogenum* utilized best at 1% on the 14th day at 5.98 pH

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value This result is relatively similar to that of Kiama *et al.* (2015), in which there was optimal growth at pH ranging at 5 – 7. It infers that the optimal pH for efficient degradation of spent engine oil by *Aspergillus niger* (F1) and *Penicillium chrysogenum* (F2) appears to be slightly acidic or in an acidic environment

The observed pH preferences highlight the significance of environmental factors in optimizing degradation processes.

CONCLUSION

Aspergillus niger and *Penicillium chrysogenum*, isolated from spent engine oil-contaminated soil, demonstrated significant potential as effective agents for the degradation of spent engine oil. Notably, *Penicillium chrysogenum* exhibited a superior capacity for degradation compared to *Aspergillus niger*. These findings highlight the promise of these fungal isolates as viable candidates for spent engine oil remediation agents, showcasing their ability to contribute to environmentally friendly and sustainable solutions for hydrocarbon-rich pollutant cleanup. The observed efficacy of *Penicillium chrysogenum* positions it as a particularly promising organism for further exploration and potential application in the field of bioremediation.

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